

Based on morphophysiological characters, F_1 fertility, variations in isozymes, and RFLP and RAPD markers, the Korean short-grained weedy rices are a relatively uniform group similar to typical japonicas, while the long-grained weedy rices are diverse and more similar to indica cultivars than to japonica cultivars. ■

Allozyme variability and inter- and intrapopulation gene diversity of *Oryza glumaepatula* in the Amazon Basin

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Oryza glumaepatula is a diploid wild rice species with the AA genome. It is found in tropical Central and South America. One of its unique ecotypes grows in the Amazon Basin, where water levels annually oscillate by as much as 10 m. The culms of these plants easily break at a specific growth stage. With no roots to anchor them to the ground, the plants float on the water and move downstream with the river current and wind.

To analyze the gene flow system and genetic diversity of populations of Amazonian *O. glumaepatula*, we examined allozyme variability of 30 loci of 16 enzymes from 34 natural populations distributed in five regions. Several parameters, including fixation index and Nei's gene

Summary of allozyme variation in *O. glumaepatula* for 30 loci of 16 enzymes within several regions: proportion of polymorphic loci (P), mean number of alleles per locus (A), observed heterozygosity (H_{obs}), and Nei's gene diversity parameters.^a

	Populations (no.)	P	A	H_{obs}	H_T^a	H_S^a	D_{ST}^a	G_{ST}^a
Rio Negro 1	3	0.20	1.27	0.002	0.059	0.040	0.018	0.310
Rio Negro 2	6	0.27	1.27	0.001	0.054	0.026	0.028	0.521
Rio Solimões 1	11	0.67	1.77	0.006	0.119	0.071	0.048	0.403
Rio Solimões 2	8	0.53	1.63	0.002	0.091	0.052	0.039	0.430
Rio Solimões 3	6	0.23	1.23	0.002	0.009	0.008	0.001	0.109
Total	34	0.73	1.93	0.003	0.109	0.043	0.067	0.610
Interregion	5	-	-	-	0.118	0.068	0.050	0.421

^a H_T = expected heterozygosity, H_S = intrapopulation gene diversity, D_{ST} = interpopulation gene diversity, G_{ST} = coefficient of genetic differentiation.

diversity, were used to assess allozyme variability of each region.

Allozymes were not so variable, although populations examined were collected from nearly 20,000 km². Overall genetic diversity had low values compared with those of the Asian wild rice, *O. rufipogon*. But population genotypes tend to be differentiated among regions isolated geographically.

In Rio Solimões, the main river of the Amazon, diversity, measured as the proportion of polymorphic loci (P), average number of alleles per locus (A), and total heterozygosity (H_T = expected heterozygosity), was found to increase when going from the upper to the lower basin (see table). Gene flow most probably proceeds in a one-way direction from the upper to the lower Amazon basin.

In Rio Negro, one of the Amazon's largest tributaries, diversity was not different between the upper and lower basins. The Rio Negro's water has poor

nutrition and low pH compared with that of other rivers, making it unfavorable for plant growth. *O. glumaepatula* colonization in the Rio Negro is limited.

Observed heterozygosities (H_{obs}) were much lower than expected, and the fixation index averaged over P was nearly equal to 1 ($F_{IS} = 0.954$). This indicates that Amazonian *O. glumaepatula* has developed self-pollination systems, enabling it to produce seed under unstable conditions. *O. glumaepatula* did not show clear population differentiation when compared with predominantly selfing annual populations of *O. rufipogon* that show higher interpopulation gene diversity (D_{ST}) rather than intrapopulation gene diversity (H_S) (see table). The degree of gene flow among populations is probably much higher in *O. glumaepatula* than in *O. rufipogon*.

The ability to float on water and self-pollination are important factors responsible for the genetic diversity observed in Amazonian *O. glumaepatula*. ■

Germplasm use in Ecuador and Bolivia

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IRRI and CIAT coordinate the International Network for Genetic Evaluation of Rice for Latin America and the Caribbean (INGER-LAC). Since its inception in 1976, countries in the region have actively used the network to exchange germplasm and information.

INGER-LAC has distributed 5,458 advanced lines to national partners through

2,272 nursery sets of 14 types from 1979 to 1993. To better understand and document the value of this service, we compared the use of introduced germplasm by national programs in Ecuador and Bolivia. We considered the number of nurseries (lines) introduced, number of varieties released from them, time taken to release a variety from an introduced line, and efforts needed to release a variety.

Information was obtained from the INGER-LAC data base. From the nurseries requested and dispatched to the two countries, we determined the number of lines introduced yearly. Ecuador released

three varieties and Bolivia, six (Tables 1 and 2).

The period covered was the time between the release of the first variety and the release of the most recent variety in each country. Having identified the first variety released, we then determined the year in which the line was introduced. The first variety was released in Ecuador in 1986, based on a line from a 1982 nursery, and in Bolivia, in 1987 from a line provided in a 1979 nursery.

Ecuador introduced 3,201 lines from 64 nurseries and released three varieties from 1982 to 1994. The national program evaluated an average of 915 lines to release a

Table 1. Germplasm use by the national program of Bolivia.

Year	Nurseries (no.)		Return (%)	Lines ^a (no.)	Varietal release		
	Dispatched	Returned			Number	Year of introduction	Time span (yr)
1979	7	3	42.9	256	0	-	-
1980	6	3	50.0	217	0	-	-
1981	9	7	77.8	201	0	-	-
1982	2	2	100.0	190	0	-	-
1983	1	1	100.0	30	0	-	-
1984	2	1	50.0	208	0	-	-
1985	2	0	0.0	111	0	-	-
1986	1	1	100.0	230	0	-	-
1987	1	1	100.0	179	2	1979/1981	8/6
1988	2	2	100.0	98	0	-	-
1989	3	3	100.0	137	0	-	-
1990	5	3	60.0	42	0	-	-
1991	6	1	16.7	101	0	-	-
1992	5	1	20.0	43	0	-	-
1993	3	2	66.7	74	2	1987/1987	6/6
1994					2	1988/1988	6/6
Total	55	31	-	2117	6	-	-
Av	3.7	2.1	56.4	141	0.4	-	6.3

^aBolivia evaluated 287 lines to release a variety. This average results from dividing the total number of lines introduced from 1979 (the year the line was introduced that gave rise to the first variety) to 1988 (the year the line was introduced that resulted in the most recently released variety) by the number of released varieties.

Table 2. Germplasm use by the national program of Ecuador.

Year	Nurseries (no.)		Return (%)	Lines ^a (no.)	Varietal release		
	Dispatched	Returned			Number	Year of introduction	Time span (yr)
1982	9	1	11.1	409	0	-	-
1983	6	2	33.3	411	0	-	-
1984	65	2	33.3	373	0	-	-
1985	6	2	33.3	336	0	-	-
1986	3	2	66.7	381	1	1982	4
1987	5	0	0.0	290	0	-	-
1988	5	0	0.0	217	0	-	-
1989	8	3	37.5	235	1	1986	3
1990	7	0	0.0	94	0	-	-
1991	3	0	0.0	214	0	-	-
1992	1	0	0.0	157	0	-	-
1993	5	0	0.0	84	0	-	-
1994					1	1990	4
Total	64	12	-	3201	3	-	11
Av	5.3	1.0	18.8	267	0.2	-	3.7

^aEcuador evaluated 915 lines to release a variety. This average results from dividing the total number of lines introduced from 1982 (the year the line was introduced that gave rise to the first variety) to 1990 (the year the line was introduced that resulted in the most recently released variety) by the number of released varieties.

commercial variety, with an average of 3.7 yr elapsing between introduction and release.

Bolivia tested 2,117 introductions from 55 nursery sets and released six varieties from 1979 to 1994. The national program evaluated an average of 287 lines per variety released, with an average of 6.3 yr between introduction and release.

Bolivia thus tested only one-third of the total lines evaluated by Ecuador to release a variety but required twice as much time to achieve the same result. These results may

be attributed to differences in the national programs' breeding strategies, target ecosystems, financial resources, and stability of breeder positions.

In conclusion, the two national programs have efficiently used germplasm distributed through INGER-LAC. If efficiency is measured as the time from introduction to release, Ecuador is more efficient than Bolivia. But if the main criterion is the number of lines evaluated to release a commercial variety, then Bolivia is more efficient than Ecuador. ■

Distribution of ribosomal DNA polymorphism in wild and cultivated rice from China

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Chinese rice comprises a major portion of the world's rice gene pool. The objective of this study was to gain understanding of the level and distribution of genetic diversity in Chinese rice germplasm using ribosomal DNA (rDNA) spacer length polymorphisms as markers.

We surveyed three sets of rice: a sample of 83 accessions of *Oryza rufipogon* that represented most of its ecogeographical range; a sample of 348 entries of cultivated *O. sativa*, including both indica and japonica varieties from almost all rice-growing areas in China; and 50 accessions of both indica and japonica cultivars from South and East Asia. Sampling emphasis was also given to a well-recognized center of diversity for cultivated rice (Yunnan in southwestern China) and to areas identified as being historically important for rice cultivation and evolution.

Statistics pertinent to levels of rDNA polymorphisms were summarized (see table). In all, 42 spacer length variants (slvs) were resolved in samples of 481 accessions. These slvs comprised a stepladder, with step sizes varying from 21 to 311 bp. Thirty-six of 42 slvs were observed in *O. rufipogon*, but only 15 slvs were detected in *O. sativa*, despite it having more accessions than *O. rufipogon*. Nine slvs occurred in both *O. rufipogon* and *O. sativa* samples, and one of them was observed at a predominantly high frequency in both *O. rufipogon* (0.310) and *O. sativa* (0.428). This slv probably represents a widely adapted allele at one of the rDNA loci.